

LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY OF BROKEN ELLIPSOIDAL INHOMOGENEITY AND CRACK EXTENDED IN PARTICLE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Composites, which contain particles or short-fibers in a ductile matrix have already used or have the potential as engineering material because of their good formability and machinability as well as improved mechanical properties. In the composites, a variety of damage modes such as fracture of reinforcements, interfacial debonding between reinforcements and matrix, and cracking in matrix develop from early stage of deformation under monotonic or cyclic loads.[1-4] The observed damage modes depend on the combination of the mechanical properties of the constituents and the in-situ interfacial strength between them. In order to extend the application of the composites and to develop a new composite system, an understanding of the micromechanism of damage process in the composites is essential. Many theories for particle or short-fiber reinforced composites were established based on the Eshelby's solution (1957) for an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity in an infinite body. [5-11] However, the corresponding solution for a broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneity has not been reported. Therefore, it is impossible to construct the theory of the composite containing cracking damage in the same scheme.

This paper deals with the load carrying capacity of intact (Fig.1(b)), broken (Fig.1(a)) and 5%-extended matrix crack proportional to broken (Fig.1(d)) ellipsoidal inhomogeneities in an infinite body and a damage theory of particle or short-fiber reinforced composites. The load carrying capacity of the broken inhomogeneity is expressed in terms of the average stress of the intact inhomogeneity and some

coefficients. Based on the finite element analyses of the intact and broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneities, the coefficients are given as functions of an aspect ratio for a variety of combinations of the elastic moduli of inhomogeneity and matrix.

2. Load Carrying Capacity of an Ellipsoidal Inhomogeneity

Load carrying capacity of an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity embedded in an infinite body can be defined as an average stress in the inhomogeneity. The load carrying capacity depends on the elastic moduli of the inhomogeneity and matrix. High average stress comparing with the remote applied stress means high load carrying capacity of the inhomogeneity. On the other hand, when the average stress is reduced by the debonding or cracking damage of the inhomogeneity, the load carrying capacity is also reduced, and the stress free in a void means that the load carrying capacity of the void is equal to zero.

Figure 1(b) shows an intact ellipsoidal inhomogeneity embedded in an infinite body under applied stress σ .

Fig. 1 Principle of superposition for a broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneity in infinite body

The elastic stiffness tensor of the infinite body (matrix) and the inhomogeneity are denoted by L_0 and L_1 , respectively. The stress of the ellipsoidal inhomogeneity σ^p is uniform and given by the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method as well known. [1]

$$\sigma^p = L_0(S - I)[(L_1 - L_0)S + L_0]^{-1}L_1(S - I)L_0^{-1}\sigma \quad (1)$$

Where, S is Eshelby's tensor which is expressed as a function of shape of the inhomogeneity and Possino's ratio of the matrix.

For an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity cracked in the cross section of xy -plane as shown in Fig. 1(a), the stress distribution in the inhomogeneity seems to be complex and its solution have not been reported as far as the authors traced references. Figure 1 shows the principle of superposition for a cracked ellipsoidal inhomogeneity in an infinite body.

The average stress in the inhomogeneity represents its load carrying capacity, and the difference between the average stresses of the intact and broken inhomogeneities indicates the loss of load carrying capacity due to the cracking damage. As shown in Fig. 1(a), the stress state in the broken inhomogeneity σ^{cp} is given by the sum of the stresses σ^p and σ^{cp*} , where σ^p the stress is in the intact inhomogeneity under the applied stress σ^p and σ^{cp*} is the broken inhomogeneity subjected to internal stress $-\sigma^p$ on the crack surface. Therefore, the average stress of the broken inhomogeneity is expressed by

$$\bar{\sigma}^{cp} = \sigma^p + \bar{\sigma}^{cp*} = \sigma^p + \mathbf{h}\sigma^p = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{h})\sigma^p = \mathbf{k}\sigma^p \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{h} is a coefficient expressing the reduction of average stress due to the cracking damage of an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity, \mathbf{k} is the ratio of the average stresses of the broken and intact inhomogeneities and \mathbf{I} was unit tensor. Once \mathbf{h} is the determined, the load carrying capacity of the broken inhomogeneity can be evaluated inclusion method. Based on the axisymmetric finite element analyses of the intact and broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneities, the matrix \mathbf{h} is obtained as a function of an aspect ratio the inhomogeneity and combination of elastic moduli of the inhomogeneity and matrix. [12]

The components of the stresses are given by $\sigma^p = [\sigma_x^p, \sigma_y^p, \sigma_z^p, \tau_{yz}^p, \tau_{zx}^p, \tau_{xy}^p]$, $\bar{\sigma}^{cp} = [\bar{\sigma}_x^{cp}, \bar{\sigma}_y^{cp}, \bar{\sigma}_z^{cp}, \bar{\tau}_{yz}^{cp}, \bar{\tau}_{zx}^{cp}, \bar{\tau}_{xy}^{cp}]$ and $\bar{\sigma}^{cp*} = [\bar{\sigma}_x^{cp*}, \bar{\sigma}_y^{cp*}, \bar{\sigma}_z^{cp*}, \bar{\tau}_{yz}^{cp*}, \bar{\tau}_{zx}^{cp*}, \bar{\tau}_{xy}^{cp*}]$. The average stress components in the broken inhomogeneity shown in

Fig.1(c) are $\bar{\sigma}^{cp*}_z$, $\bar{\sigma}^{cp*}_x$ and $\bar{\sigma}^{cp*}_y$ due to internal stress $-\sigma^p_z$ on the crack surface, $\bar{\tau}^{cp*}_{yz}$ due to $-\tau^p_{yz}$, and $\bar{\tau}^{cp*}_{zx}$ due to $-\tau^p_{zx}$. Therefore, we have

$$\mathbf{k} = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{h}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & h_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & h_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 + h_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 + h_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 + h_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

in the matrix form. Furthermore, in the case of the axisymmetric ellipsoidal inhomogeneity, $h_{13} = h_{23}$ and $h_{44} = h_{55}$ relations are obtained. As a result, once the three components, h_{33} , h_{13} and h_{44} are obtained, the average stress of the broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneity can be evaluated by Eqs.(1) and (2). Out of the three components, h_{33} and h_{13} are determined by the analysis under uniaxial tension, and h_{44} is by the analysis under pure shear.

3. Numerical Procedure

Elastic stress analyses of intact and damaged ellipsoidal inhomogeneities embedded in an infinite body under uniaxial tension as shown in Fig.1 were carried out based on the axisymmetric finite element method using the quadrilateral 8-node isoparametric elements. Mesh division was carried out for a wide ellipsoidal domain including an inhomogeneity in the center, and uniaxial uniform tensile stress in the z -axis direction is applied on the surface of the domain as boundary condition. The size of the inhomogeneity is denoted by $2a$ and $2b$ in r (x and y) direction and z direction, respectively. On the same finite element meshes, the node points on the z - and r -axes were fixed for the intact inhomogeneity, and the node points on the z - and r -axes except crack plane were fixed for the cracked inhomogeneity. In the analyses, an aspect ratio (b/a) of the inhomogeneity and the combination in the elastic moduli of the inhomogeneity and matrix were widely changed. The average stress in the intact and cracked inhomogeneities were calculated and used as the load carrying capacity. [12]

4. Numerical Results and Discussion

4.1 Stress distribution in and around an inhomogeneity

Stress distributions of the intact and cracked inhomogeneities are shown for the case in which Young's modulus ratio is $E_p/E_m=5.0$ and Poisson's

ratios are $\nu_m=0.3$ for the matrix and $\nu_p=0.17$ for the inhomogeneity. The aspect ratios are 0.5 (oblate spheroid), 1.0 (sphere) and 3.0 (prolate spheroid). The stress in the intact inhomogeneities is uniform as well known as Eshelby's solution for ellipsoidal inclusion. The maximum tensile stress in the matrix is created in the region near the pole of the inhomogeneity. On the other hand, in the case of the cracked inhomogeneity, the stress is released on the region near the crack surface and becomes nonuniform in the inhomogeneity, and it concentrates at the crack tip region and the pole of the inhomogeneity in the surrounding matrix. [12] The stress distributions of σ_z along the z -axis and r -axis are shown in Fig. 2 for the intact inhomogeneities and in Fig. 3 for the broken and 5%-extended matrix crack proportional to broken inhomogeneities, respectively. These distributions were obtained by the data at the Gauss points close to the z -axis and r -axis. It is found in Fig. 2 that the uniform stress in the intact inhomogeneity increases with increasing its aspect ratio. This means that longer fiber has larger load carrying capacity.

Fig. 2 Stress distribution (σ_z/σ) along the z - and r -axis for an intact inhomogeneity under uniaxial tension

Fig. 3 Stress distribution (σ_z/σ) along the z - and r -axis for an broken inhomogeneity and 5%-extended matrix crack proportional to broken inhomogeneity to under uniaxial tension

In Fig. 3(a) for the cracked inhomogeneity and it's the crack extended to matrix, the stress is equals to zero at the crack surface and increases with the distance from the crack surface, and then the maximum stress is obtained at the pole of the inhomogeneity.

It is found from the above results that the stress distributions in and around an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity in an infinite body under uniaxial tension become more complex by the cracking damage, and that the cracked inhomogeneity still maintains a large amount of load carrying capacity. In the case of the cracked ellipsoidal inhomogeneity, a singular stress field is dominant around the crack tip and it is very important on the discussion of the fracture behavior from the crack tip. In the present paper, however, the stress singularity at the crack tip is not referred any more but the load carrying capacity will be intensely discussed.

4. 2 Load Carrying Capacity

As mentioned previously, the load carrying capacity of an ellipsoidal inhomogeneity embedded in a matrix is defined by its average stress. In this section, the average stress in the intact and broken inhomogeneities in an infinite body under uniaxial tension is calculated based on the result of the finite element analyses, and the load carrying capacity of these inhomogeneities is discussed. In the axisymmetric finite element analysis the stress components in z -axis, radial and circumferential directions, $\bar{\sigma}_z^p$, $\bar{\sigma}_r^p$ and $\bar{\sigma}_\theta^p$, are obtained. Here, the stress components in the rectangular coordinate system $\bar{\sigma}_z^p$ and $\bar{\sigma}_z^p = \bar{\sigma}_y^p$ transferred from $\bar{\sigma}_z^p$, $\bar{\sigma}_r^p$ and $\bar{\sigma}_\theta^p$ are used for the discussion.

Fig. 4 Stress of an intact inhomogeneity in infinite body under uniaxial tension as a function of an aspect ratio

Figure 4 (a) and (b) show the stresses σ_z^p and σ_x^p of the intact inhomogeneity in an infinite body under uniaxial tension as a function of an aspect ratio for various combinations in the elastic moduli of inhomogeneity and matrix. The solid lines and plots indicate the results of Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method (Eq. (1)) and the results of the finite element analyses, respectively. Good agreement between both results shows that the present finite element analyses of the ellipsoidal domain containing the inhomogeneity in the center well simulate an inhomogeneity in an infinite body. It is found from Fig. 4(a) that with increasing the aspect ratio, the stress in tensile direction σ_z^p increases for the Young's modulus ratio of $E_p/E_m > 1$, and decreases for $E_p/E_m < 1$. The stress perpendicular to tensile direction σ_x^p shown in Fig. 4(b) is always negative, and it depends on the Young's modulus ratio at the region of low aspect ratio but converges to around -0.06 with increasing the aspect ratio.

As shown in the previous section, the stress in the inhomogeneity is released by the cracking damage, but the cracked inhomogeneity still has a large amount of load carrying capacity. From Eq. (2), relations between the average stresses of the broken and intact inhomogeneities under multi-axial tension are expressed by

$$\bar{\sigma}_z^{cp} = (1 + h_{33})\sigma_z^p \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_x^{cp} = \sigma_x^p + h_{13}\sigma_z^p \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_y^{cp} = \sigma_y^p + h_{13}\sigma_z^p \quad (6)$$

Using equations (4) and (5), the coefficients and are determined from the numerical results of the average stresses of intact and broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneity.

Fig. 5 Coefficient (h_{33}) and ratio of load carrying capacity as a function of an aspect ratio.

(a) Intact and broken (b) Intact and 5%- extended inhomogeneities matrix crack proportional to broken inhomogeneity

Fig. 6 Coefficient (h_{13}) as a function of an aspect ratio

Figures 5, 6 show relationship between the coefficients h_{33} , h_{13} , and the aspect ratio for various combinations in the elastic moduli. Since the load carrying capacity of the cracked inhomogeneity under multi-axial tension can be easily evaluated by the above equations from the average stress of the intact inhomogeneity obtained by the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method, these coefficients are very important.

Hereafter, we discuss in more detail the change of the load carrying capacity due to cracking damage of the ellipsoidal inhomogeneity under uniaxial tension. Figure 5 also exhibits a ratio of the load carrying capacity $\bar{\sigma}_z^{cp} / \sigma_z^p$ which is defined by the ratio of the average stress in the broken and 5%-extended matrix crack proportional to broken inhomogeneity ($\bar{\sigma}_z^{cp}$) to the stress in the intact inhomogeneity (σ_z^p), when it is observed for a scale of the right hand side. As shown in Fig. 6, the load carrying capacity ratio is always smaller than one, i.e. the inhomogeneity reduces its load carrying capacity by the cracking damage and crack extended to matrix. It is found that the load carrying capacity ratio increases with increasing the aspect ratio and depends on the combination of the elastic moduli. The load carrying capacity ratio is equal to zero for a penny shape inhomogeneity ($b/a=0$), while it approaches to unit for a continuous long fiber ($b/a=\infty$). This means that a penny shape inhomogeneity loses completely the load carrying capacity by the cracking damage while the infinitely long fiber in an infinite body never loses it. With increasing Young's modulus ratio E_p/E_m , the load carrying capacity ratio increases in the region of low aspect ratio and decreases in the region of high aspect ratio. Particularly, the

influence of E_p/E_m to the load carrying capacity is drastic for the inhomogeneity with low aspect ratio. This suggests that in a composite reinforced with ellipsoidal inhomogeneity with low aspect ratio a stiffer inhomogeneity maintains higher load carrying capacity after cracking damage.

5. Conclusions

Axisymmetric finite element analyses have been carried out on the elastic stress distribution and load carrying capacity of intact and broken ellipsoidal inhomogeneities embedded in an infinite body under uniaxial tension. Conclusions obtained from the numerical results are summarized as follows:

(1) For the intact inhomogeneity, the stress distribution is uniform in the inhomogeneity and nonuniform in the surrounding matrix, as well known as Eshelby's solution. On the other hand, for the broken inhomogeneity and its crack extended to matrix, the stress in the region near the crack surface in the inhomogeneity is considerably released and the stress distribution becomes more complex.

(2) The average stress in the broken inhomogeneity is expressed by the average stress of the intact inhomogeneity. Based on the numerical results, the coefficients in the expression describing this relationship under multi-axial tension are obtained as a function of the aspect ratio of the inhomogeneity.

(3) The inhomogeneity in an infinite body loses load carrying capacity by cracking damage, but the broken inhomogeneity and its crack extended to matrix still maintains it to some extent. The ratio of the load carrying capacity of the intact, broken and crack extended to matrix proportional to broken inhomogeneities is given as a function of the aspect ratio of the inhomogeneity. It is found that the broken inhomogeneity with higher aspect ratio maintains higher load carrying capacity than one with low aspect ratio.

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